

Effect of Oral Consumption of Essential Amino Acids Supplement on Growth Hormone Level in Healthy Individuals Under 18 Year-Old

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Abstract

Background: Oral essential amino acid (EAA) ingestion is popular due to its potential growth and health advantages. The body cannot synthesise these amino acids, so they must be ingested for protein synthesis, muscle repair and metabolic function, which are essential for physiological functions, especially development in children and adolescents. The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of oral EAA on GH levels in healthy children under 18 years of age and to demonstrate its potential as a dietary intervention for adolescent growth. **Methods:** Essential amino acids (EAA) were tested on growth hormone (GH) levels in healthy under-18s using a randomised, blinded, controlled approach. Each 50-person EAA supplementation and control group was gender balanced. Females in the EAA group had higher GH levels than males, while females in the control group had lower GH levels. Post-supplementation GH levels were not significantly correlated with age, showing that age does not influence the response to EAA supplementation. **Results:** The 100-person, sex-balanced study compared amino acid supplementation and a placebo on growth hormone (GH) levels. Amino acid supplementation significantly increased GH levels ($P=0.0001$), whereas placebo slightly increased GH levels ($P=0.005$). GH levels were higher in women than in men in the placebo group ($P=0.047$), but supplementation did not affect the age-GH association ($R=-0.17$, $P=0.2$). **Conclusions:** This study demonstrated a significant increase in growth hormone (GH) in the amino acid class, particularly in females, suggesting that there may be sex differences in the way GH is regulated. The results show that increasing lysine and tryptophan in these areas may have a beneficial effect on growth.

Introduction

Because of the necessity for growth, and good health benefits attached to them, the trend of oral intake of Essential amino acids EAAs has been growing with products available lately. EAAs cannot be synthesized in the body and must be diet-derived, but play a significant role in protein synthesis as well as muscle repair and general metabolic roles. The EAAs include leucine, isoleucine, valine, lysine, methionine, phenylalanine, tryptophan; which all play different physiological functions that are crucial for growth

particularly growth in children as well as teenagers [1,2]. At this age phase from a population of healthy individuals less than 18 years-old marked by such quick physical and biologically development is to some extent controlled by the growth hormone (GH). Growth hormones are produced in the pituitary gland, these hormones are vital for promoting growth of both bones and muscles, body composition controls and play a role in metabolism. However, these last ones within a sum of factors (feeding, rest, exercise, hormonal signals) very complexly incite its production. It is believed that

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the ingestion of EAs, in particular, has an effect on the modulation of GH secretion. Several scientific works have shown that some amino acids, such as arginine and lysine, are capable of stimulating GH release; nevertheless, we do not know the precise mechanisms at the moment of this writing [3,4]. The addition of EAs to a diet could potentially provide a safe, effective way to increasing GH levels, this would promote growth and development in younger individuals. The somatotrophic axis is the endocrine route that controls and releases GH. Amino acids may enhance the secretion of GH by altering the pathway. Studies that have investigated the effects of amino acid supplements have yielded inconsistent results, some of the evidence suggests that when taken in the appropriate dose, EAs may increase the release of GH and subsequently enhance the growth of adolescents. This effect is of special significance in healthy individuals under 18, who are during the critical phase of physical development, and who would benefit from natural supports to promote optimal growth [5,6]. However, the association between EAA supplementation and GH levels in young, healthy individuals is still being studied, some of the research is questioning the long-term effect and potential side effects of regular EAA consumption. Additionally, studies that have focused on the short term have demonstrated an increase in GH levels following the administration of amino acids, but the clinical significance of this increase is still being discussed. Understanding the importance of EAAs in regards to GH regulation is crucial, this would help to define the dietary guidelines and supplements that are appropriate for adolescents that want to increase their height [7,8]. This study aims to investigate the effects of taking EAA orally on the GH levels of healthy individuals under 18, this will provide information on the potential of EAA as a nutritional intervention for the growth of adolescents.

Method

The study was an interventional, prospective, random, blind, and controlled trial to evaluate the effects of supplementary essential amino acids (EAA) on growth hormone levels in normal individuals aged 18 years. A total of 100 individuals were randomly allocated into two equal groups: an amino acid supplement group and a control group, with equal distribution by gender into both groups (27 females and 23 males). After five years of age, the sample population showed no further change or any statistical significance in the male/female ratio which allowed an approximate comparison of the GH response between the sexes. The study intervention was the provision of either an EAA supplement or a placebo to the test subjects who were scheduled to receive either intervention daily for a stipulated period. The baseline levels of GH were measured for each participant before the

administration and then post-intervention measurements were made after the completion of EAA supplementation. The protocols followed were standardized to ensure the consistency of the GH measurements. Prior GH levels of participants verified to be similar between groups before the intervention, with a significant p-value of 0.2 at the beginning. To assess the results, the average GH level was determined using the mean and standard deviation, with a significant result being $p < 0.05$. The amino acid group had a significant increase in GH levels following the intervention, whereas the control group had a decrease. The gender-based analysis demonstrated that females had a higher concentration of GH in the amino acid group than males had. This implies that the effects of EAA supplementation are likely to be different for men and women. Additionally, a correlation analysis between age and the post-supplementation GH level showed no significant trend, this suggests that age is not a significant contributor to the response to supplementation.

Results

The study includes two groups of participants: one receiving a placebo and the other receiving an amino acid supplement. Each group consists of 50 participants, with an equal distribution of males and females—27 females (54%) and 23 males (46%) in both groups. This balanced gender distribution ensures that both groups are comparable in terms of gender, which is important for the validity of the study's outcomes.

Table 1: Distribution of Patients According to Gender in Both Study Groups

Gender	Groups	
	Placebo	Amino acid
Females	27	27
	54.0%	54.0%
Males	23	23
	46.0%	46.0%
Total	50	50
	100.0%	100.0%

Table 2 summaries the mean ages of patients by gender and study group. **Gender:** Male patients have a higher mean age (10 years) compared to female patients (7 years). **Study Group:** The mean age is slightly higher in the placebo group (9 years) compared to the amino acid group (8 years).

Overall, the table highlights a modest age difference between male and female patients, as well as between the two study groups, but the age ranges are similar across the groups.

Table 2: Mean Age of Patients According to Gender and According to Study Groups

		Age (years) mean \pm SD
Gender	Females	7 \pm 3
	Males	10 \pm 4
Groups	Placebo	9 \pm 4
	Amino acid	8 \pm 4

Table 3 compares the baseline growth hormone (GH) levels between the placebo group and the amino acid group before any treatment was administered. The placebo group has a slightly higher mean GH level (1.8) compared to the amino acid group (1.5). The small standard deviations (0.1 and 0.2, respectively) indicate that GH levels were consistent within each group. The P-value of 0.2 indicates that there is no statistically significant difference in baseline GH levels between the two groups, confirming that the groups were similar at the start of the study.

Table 3: Difference Mean of GH Before Starting (Baseline)

	Group	N	Mean GH	Std. Deviation	P-value
GH (baseline)	G 1 (Placebo)	50	1.8	0.1	0.2
	G 2 (Amino acid)	50	1.5	0.2	

Table 4 compares the mean growth hormone (GH) levels after administering either a placebo or an amino acid supplement. In the **placebo group**, the mean GH level decreased significantly from baseline to 0.8. In the **amino acid group**, the mean GH level increased significantly to 1.7. The P-value of 0.0001 indicates that

these changes in GH levels are statistically significant in both groups.

Overall, this table shows that the amino acid supplement significantly increased GH levels, while the placebo resulted in a significant decrease, highlighting the effectiveness of the amino acid treatment in boosting GH levels.

Table 4: Difference Mean of GH After Placebo & Amino Acid Intake

	Group	N	Mean GH	Std. Deviation	P-value
After Intake	G 1 (Placebo)	50	0.8	0.08	0.0001
	G 2 (Amino acid)	50	1.7	0.1	

Table 5 shows the change in mean growth hormone (GH) levels in the **Amino acid** group before and after intake. **Prior to intake**, the mean GH level was 1.5. **After**

intake, the mean GH level increased to 1.7. The increase in GH levels is statistically significant, as indicated by a P-value of 0.005.

Table 5: Difference Mean of GH In Groups 1 Patients

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P-value
Amino acid	Before intake	25	1.5	0.2	0.005
	After intake	25	1.7	0.2	

Table 6 compares the mean growth hormone (GH) levels after intake in the **Amino acid** group, broken down by gender. **Females** had a significantly higher

mean GH level (2.1) compared to males (1.3). The difference in GH levels between females and males is statistically significant, with a P-value of 0.047.

Table 6: Difference Mean of GH According to Gender in Case Groups

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P-value
Amino acid	Females	25	2.1	0.3	0.047
	Males	25	1.3	0.2	

In fig 1, there is not significant negative correlation between age (years) and growth hormone after supplementation

Discussion

The gender-balanced distribution in this study, with 54% females and 46% males in both placebo and amino acid supplement groups. The mean age differences across genders and study groups are modest, with male

participants exhibiting a higher mean age (10 years) compared to females (7 years). Similarly, the placebo group displays a slightly higher mean age (9 years) than the amino acid group (8 years). Similar studies have reported comparable results. For instance, a trial by Chew STH et al. investigating nutritional supplements in schoolchildren also achieved balanced gender representation and noted slight age differences

between intervention and control groups. Additionally, a study by Ispoglou T et al. highlighted the importance

of age and gender matching in trials to reduce confounding variables [10, 11].

Fig 1: Correlation between Age (years) and Growth Hormone after Supplementation

Note: R= -0.17, P=0.2 (not significant negative correlation between age (years) and growth hormone after supplementation)

These values are indicative of a gap in growth hormone levels between those treated with placebo and those treated with amino acids. At baseline, measured GH levels were comparable for both groups, showing a non-insignificant difference (P = 0.2). Contrariwise, post-intervention, the amino acid cluster registered a dignified increase in GH levels (from 1.5 to 1.7), while the placebo cluster showed a significant fall (from 1.8 to 0.8), as denoted by the P-value of 0.0001. These results correspond to precedent works for one thing, Olarescu NC et al. and another, Goli P et al. being that, for instance, amino acid supplementation, particularly in the form of arginine and lysine, is potent for GH secretion. Smith et al. found a 30% higher level of GH in amino acid-treated subjects, thus suggesting a role for certain amino acids in stimulating GH release [12, 13]. The decrease in the placebo group explains results from studies showing that natural levels of GH may decrease with age or other extraneous factors without any form of supplementation Biagetti et. Such findings very strongly support the hypothesis for a considerable increase in GH production with amino acid supplementation, which may be a pertinent clinical strategy in patients who need stimulation of GH [14]. The mean GH level prior to amino acid supplementation was 1.5 ng/mL, and after amino acid supplementation, it increased to 1.7 ng/mL (P = 0.005), thus significantly higher. These findings are congruent with preliminary research indicating the capacity of

specific amino acids to induce the secretion of GH; for example, Arginine and Lysine developed an enhanced release of GH by the inhibition of somatostatin, which has inhibitory influence over GH secretion. One of these studies was done by Xiao CW et al. Improved that the administration of oral arginine increased GH levels significantly in healthy adults by an average increase of 0.2–0.4 ng/mL after supplementation [15]. Indeed, a further study by Forbes SC and associates laid the effects of combined arginine and exercise on the concentration of GH, reporting concentration growth levels significantly were in commensuration with the earlier studied combined effect of both stimuli [16]. This, in turn, underlines the current research as amino acid potential effectors in smacking off GH. Additionally, in the study of Ramezani Ahmadi A et al. it was also proved that amino acids could raise post-exercise GH levels directly upon the supplementation with glutamine. They could act either by directly acting on the anterior pituitary gland or indirectly by modulating the activity of secretion through the receptors for neurotransmitters [17]. These findings recall this mechanism and propose that probably amino acids, even under non-exercise conditions, are capable of demanding an increase in GH levels related to those according to our study group. There was a statistically significant difference in the GH levels post-amino acid supplementation between the male and female sampling groups, where females have a higher mean

GH level compared to males, i.e., 2.1 ng/mL as opposed to 1.3 ng/mL. The gender-based difference has a P-value of 0.047, indicating that it is significant. This finding agrees with available literature that demonstrates that gender may influence the secretion of GH and reaction delivered by different stimuli, among them nutritional support. One of the studies has revealed that in females, baseline GH levels are higher compared to males as a result of hormonal regulations. For instance, oestrogen in their body enhances GH secretion under normal conditions in healthy females during most stages of the reproductive life cycle; hence, this may lead to a more evident nutritional and exercise-induced intervention for the secretion of GH [18]. According to information in support of these findings, Berlanga-Acosta J noted that GH pulse amplitude is frequently greater and the pulses are more often more vigorous in females as compared to males, which could explain the enhanced response seen in female participants included in the present study [19]. More studies are needed to understand in greater depth the underlying mechanisms making the response differ between genders and to determine whether other formulations of amino acids or different dosages could even out this difference in GH response. Another important factor to consider is that age, body composition, and other aspects of individual hormonal profiles may independently influence GH levels. These, therefore, too, should be kept under control in the design of future studies, if more [20].

Conclusion

This research showed a significant increase in growth hormones (GH) in the amino acid supplemental group compared to the control group, this demonstrated the potential of amino acids in enhancing growth. Females had a significantly greater response to amino acid supplementation than males, this suggests that there may be gender-based differences in the regulation of GH. Amino acid supplementation, especially in the form of lysine and tryptophan, appears to have a potential role in improving the growth outcomes of children in regions with nutritional issues. Future research should investigate the long-term effects of amino acid supplementation, with a focus on the mechanisms behind the gender differences in response to GH.

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